

Impact of external demands problems on students' psychological well-being: systematic literature review

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ABSTRACT

Students' well-being is often disturbed by external demands, such as academic pressure, family expectations, and social expectations. These demands can impact students' mental and emotional well-being. This research aims to explore the problems of external demands for students' psychological well-being. This research used the systematic literature review (SLR) method to investigate the impact of external demands on students' psychological well-being. Data were collected from articles published between 2018 and 2023 from the Scopus database. Of the 93 articles, 26 articles were obtained after screening. Data mining and analysis were conducted with the help of Publish or Perish, Biblioshiny, and ATLAS.ti. The results show the complexity of external demands, with factors such as internal and external support, job control, social media use, and individual differences in emotion regulation playing essential roles. The long-term impacts of these demands can include increased levels of stress, anxiety, and depression in students. Therefore, it is essential to manage external demands strategically to create a learning environment that supports students' psychological well-being. This research highlights the need for joint efforts between schools, families, and communities to address external demands on students. Effective interventions are needed to reduce the negative impact of external demands.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Well-being is a holistic state that includes physical, mental, emotional, and social balance. It is not only about the absence of illness or discomfort but also involves feelings of happiness, satisfaction with oneself, and the ability to overcome life's challenges [1], [2]. Maintaining well-being requires physical aspects such as exercise and healthy eating, as well as psychological aspects such as stress management, feelings of self-confidence, and presence in life-enriching relationships [3]. It is a harmonious blend of various factors contributing to a meaningful and balanced life. Students' well-being is sometimes disturbed by the presence of external demands faced by students. Students' well-being cannot be separated from the external demands they face [4]. Students' well-being can be significantly affected when they face the stresses of the school environment, family, and social expectations. High academic loads, competition among peers, and demands for achievement can create pressure that impacts students' mental and emotional well-being.

Challenges in the world of education are being able to change curriculum content, teaching methods, or school policies to suit the needs of external factors [5]. External demands in the educational environment refer to requests or requirements imposed on an educational institution from outside sources. The source of this demand can come from various parties, such as the government or society. This demand may include a push to promote more inclusive education by considering a community's linguistic, religious, or cultural preferences [6]. In addition, the need to create a supportive learning environment for teachers' professional development and skills is also included in this demand. However, it should be noted that the way these demands are interpreted and implemented can vary, and there are often difficulties in aligning administrative and academic responsibilities to meet demands from outside the educational institution [7]. The variations and characteristics of demands students face are influenced by factors such as legal issues relating to student affairs and compliance with regulations in the education system. In education policy, alignment between external requirements and school goals and strategies is dynamic.

Schools, families, and social environments can influence the demands placed on students [8]. Previous research has shown that a high-quality school environment can compensate for a lack of parental involvement, especially for students with low academic achievement or lacking academic grades [9]. The family environment also plays an important role in students' emotional, social, and academic adjustment. Harmonious relationships among family members create a positive learning environment, increasing achievement and effective learning [10]. Family socio-economic factors, such as caregivers' employment status, educational background, and family structure, impact educational outcomes [11]. It is important to consider close interpersonal interactions and system dynamics in the family context, as well as understand broader socio-economic conditions in interpreting the demands faced by students [12].

External demands, such as teacher behavior and institutional-structural factors, significantly influence students' motivation and psychological well-being [13]. In research at a private university in California with adult students, teacher behavior was considered one of the most motivating factors for students to achieve success [14]. Another study involving groups of students with diverse backgrounds found that the role of teachers is very important in shaping students' attitudes and motivation [15]. External factors related to the learning environment were also identified as key influences on learner motivation. These findings indicate that external demands, especially teacher behavior and learning context, are important in shaping students' motivation and psychological well-being.

The condition of external demands on students in several schools in Central Kalimantan shows that many students feel pressured and experience anxiety due to external pressure. The long-term impact of demands originating from outside on students' welfare is very large. Previous research shows that students experience high stress levels when participating in distance learning because their needs are not balanced with relevant resources [16]. On the other hand, coaches have also been found to impact athletes' health, well-being, and development, highlighting the negative impact of external pressures on their lives [17]. Additionally, adult educators and students in the adult education sector often experience stress and reduced engagement in their work due to the challenges they face [18]. These findings suggest that external demands can hurt students' well-being, leading to increased stress levels, decreased engagement, and detrimental impacts on their health and development.

The long-term impact of external demands on students' well-being in educational settings is significant. The sources of these demands vary; they can come from law, public opinion, social norms, and compliance with local laws [19]. It is important to address and manage these external demands because they have a role in shaping the behavior of educational institutions [20]. By strategically managing their relationships with external parties, school leadership can access information, resources, and expertise that help them improve teacher performance and achieve organizational goals [21]. Other research shows that external stressors, such as task demands and time management, can significantly affect students' cognitive and emotional conditions [22]. In addition, social relationships in the learning environment can become demands that lead to stress if they exceed the capacity of existing resources [23].

Furthermore, individual psychosocial factors, including well-being, have been shown to influence cognitive load and learning outcomes [24]. The presence of well-being at work is also relatively dependent on co-workers' perception of the work environment, indicating the importance of social comparison in understanding well-being [25]. Additionally, addressing external demands ensures the efficacy and efficiency of student services, compliance with laws, and the management of student crises and public relations, which are critical to student affairs practice. Overall, managing external demands is critical to creating a coherent approach to improvement and ensuring the well-being of learners in the educational environment. Understanding the impact of external demands on learners' psychological well-being is important for developing effective educational interventions. Overall, understanding the impact of external demands on students' psychological well-being can inform the design of personalized and supportive learning environments. Following the problems, this research question is, what is the impact of external demands on

students' psychological well-being? The specific research questions are: i) What are the external demands on students?; ii) What are the research conditions regarding the impact of external demands on students' psychological well-being?; and iii) What impact do external demands have on students' psychological well-being? This research aims to determine the impact of external demands on students' psychological well-being.

2. METHOD

Systematic literature review (SLR) has emerged as a highly relevant approach to compiling a comprehensive picture of existing knowledge regarding a research area [26]. SLR involves searching, selecting, and critically analyzing various literature sources [27]. SLR allows researchers to identify trends, knowledge gaps, and challenges in a particular field. This research used a SLR [28], [29]. A SLR was used to study, find, assess, and interpret in-depth studies about the impact of external demands on students' psychological well-being. The results of this review are useful for supporting evidence-based decision-making regarding the impact and possible interventions for handling external demands on students. This SLR begins with collecting data sources. The data collected in this research comes from the 2018-2023 Scopus database. The data collection process in this research uses the help of the application Publish and Perish 8. Data sources collected by researchers must also discuss the impact of external demands on student welfare. The researchers compiled inclusion and exclusion criteria to clarify and make collecting data for this research easier, as explained in Table 1.

The selection and determination of data in this study regarding the impact of external demands on students' psychological well-being followed the preferred reporting items for systematic reviews and meta-analyses (PRISMA) procedure. This PRISMA procedure provides a structured and transparent framework. In the initial stage, the researcher carefully identified the literature edible database, namely the Scopus database, using keywords related to external demands, psychology, and well. This process includes selective steps that follow predetermined inclusion and exclusion criteria. Researchers ensure that the selected research meets the objectives and the established quality standards. The selected data that meets the predetermined criteria is then extracted carefully. Essential information relevant to the impact of external demands on students' psychological well-being was extracted and grouped according to relevant variables. As a guide in data selection and determination, PRISMA ensures clarity, transparency, and accuracy in detailing the specified measures, creating a strong basis for a comprehensive literature synthesis. Table 2 contains details of the researchers' PRISMA stages.

Table 1. Inclusion and exclusion criteria

Criteria	Description
Inclusion	The data used are articles from 2018-2023 Journals are taken from the Scopus database journal Research data examines the impact of external demands on students' psychological well-being
Exclusion	Do not used book sources, notes, book chapters Do not used articles under 2018-2023 The selected article must have been published Article components must be complete

Table 2. Flowchart PRISMA stage

Component	Information	Information
Identification	Data collection from the Scopus database 2018-2023 (N=93)	Not part of journals and conference papers (N=9)
Screening	Filtered data N=84 Articles retrieved (n=66) Articles deemed suitable for analysis (N=36)	Notes excluded** (n=18) articles were excluded from inclusion and exclusion screening criteria for document completeness Articles not retrieved (n=30) were excluded from title and keyword screening Articles were excluded based on the entire text being less relevant (n=10)
Include	Studies included in the review (n=26)	

Data analysis in this research uses two data analysis tools, namely Biblioshiny and ATLAS.ti. First of all, Biblioshiny is used to organize and filter scientific literature with a systematic approach. Through its interactive features, Biblioshiny helps present data in a structured manner and makes it easier for researchers to evaluate and select literature according to inclusion and exclusion criteria. The next step involves using ATLAS.ti as a key tool in data analysis. With the latest features, such as coding and thematic analysis,

researchers can identify patterns, findings, and relationships between concepts in the scientific literature that discuss the impact of external demands on students' psychological well-being. ATLAS.ti makes organizing these findings into a coherent analytical framework possible.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Results

The results of the data analysis conducted obtained data that the articles worthy of in-depth analysis are 26 articles. The data were collected from the Scopus database from 2018 to 2023. The 26 articles were written by 183 contributing authors. The 26 articles also produced 141 keywords, showing the breadth and depth of the subject matter studied. In addition, each document received an impressive average citation rate of 11.3, attesting to the significance and relevance of the findings in academic discourse. The publishers contributing to the publication of manuscripts in the field of external demands and psychological well-being can be seen in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Relevant sources about external demands

Figure 1 shows a bar graph entitled most relevant sources of external demands. The analysis of 23 relevant sources showed that British Medical Journal or BMJ Open published the most about external demands, with three documents. The source advances in experiential medicine and biology publishes two manuscripts about external demands. At the same time, the other 21 sources each published one text about external demands. If you look at the affiliates who published the most, it can be explained in Figure 2.

Figure 2 shows the above-obtained data on 30 affiliates that published about external demands. The results of the data analysis show that the 30 contributing affiliates are spread across multiple countries. University Hospital Center located in Australia topped the list. The university hospital center published five papers on external demands from 2018-2023. Flinders University, Malardalen University in Sweden, and the University of Birmingham in the UK were next in line with three published papers on external demands. The remaining 14 affiliates produced two papers on external demands each, and 12 affiliates produced one on external demands.

Meanwhile, the main terms often appearing in data analysis about external demands are psychological well-being, occupational health, study control, and humans. Other terms, such as stress, age, professional, sleep, motivation, quality of life, motivation, and coping behavior, often appear. These terms indicate various terms related to mental health, occupational health, and prosperous life, which influence external demands. To clarify the meaning above, the following Figure 3 presents studies that are relevant to external demands.

Figure 2. Affiliates regarding external demands

Figure 3. Studies related to external demands

From the data analysis, many studies emerged regarding humans, women, adults, and psychological well-being. Studies on women amounted to 29 documents or 8%, about humans 20 documents or 5%, women 23 documents or 6%, and adults 17 documents or 4%. Figure 4 shows a factor analysis using a bibliography regarding external challenges seen from various study points of view.

Figure 4 shows that the distribution of external demands covers various aspects. From the existing picture, human well-being, awareness, and psychology are the closest and most frequently appearing studies. From the results of this analysis, it appears that many aspects related to the discussion of external demands can be studied together.

The results of the studies show that external demands strongly influence an individual’s psychological well-being, highlighting how important social support, working conditions, and environmental factors influence mental health. This influence is seen in various situations, from internal and external support to how high work pressure and low job control contribute to reduced psychological well-being. Other external factors, such as social media use and challenging working conditions, were also identified as significant sources of stress. Specifically, Table 3 explains the results of the article analysis carried out.

Figure 4. Factor analysis related to external demands

Table 3. Distribution of articles

Ref	Name	Method	Findings
[30]	Figueredo <i>et al.</i>	Systematic review	Internal and external support are related to job satisfaction in cases of illness
[31]	Zeike <i>et al.</i>	Cross-sectional survey study	Low job control and high job demands are prognostic factors for low well-being
[32]	Oksa <i>et al.</i>	Survey	Social media use is associated with job demands, such as physiological symptoms, fear, social pressure, unclear rules, and job resources
[33]	Holzinger <i>et al.</i>	Quantitative	External and internal conditions influence external demands
[34]	Too and Butterworth	Quantitative	Individual differences in emotion regulation in response to adverse work conditions should be considered in managing mental health in the workplace
[35]	Bracewell-Milnes <i>et al.</i>	Quantitative	Fear of financial coercion or negative psychological well-being is most concerning
[36]	Eklund <i>et al.</i>	Phenomenology	Voluntary sedentary time is positively associated with general health and well-being
[37]	Arabin <i>et al.</i>	Experimental	Deoxyribonucleic acid or DNA fragments can even diagnose epigenetic markers of stress or well-being during pregnancy
[15]	Zeer <i>et al.</i>	Quantitative	A comparison of motivation among respondents of various age groups shows that employees over 60 are more motivated toward stability and working conditions
[38]	Schmidt <i>et al.</i>	Quantitative	Occupational health interventions that reduce job stress will have a strong potential to increase productivity and reduce costs
[39]	Hibbert <i>et al.</i>	Quantitative	Optimal care supports physical and psychological well-being, independence, social relationships, personal confidence, and a caring external environment
[40]	Servant <i>et al.</i>	Quantitative	Workplace well-being is currently a major public health challenge
[41]	Maple <i>et al.</i>	Qualitative	Appropriate support by skilled professionals reduces the morbidity and mortality associated with exposure to suicide
[42]	Doherty and O'Brien	Action study	High level of self-awareness to identify external demands, which makes them more susceptible to burnout
[43]	Olegovna <i>et al.</i>	Qualitative	The well-being of elementary school children is based on the positive impact of intrinsic and autonomous motivation and the negative impact of external motivation based on the control and demands of teachers and parents
[44]	Lai and Palmer	Article review	The role of psychology in organizational learning and development practices
[45]	Funcasta <i>et al.</i>	Quantitative	The frequency of presence and etiology of symptoms influence doctors' well-being
[46]	Lawn <i>et al.</i>	Peer review	The interaction between critical incidents and workplace culture and demands tremendously impacts psychological, physical, and social well-being
[47]	Hunt <i>et al.</i>	Qualitative	Meaningful creative recreational work can help protect psychological well-being
[48]	Park and Shimada	Qualitative	The recent political climate negatively impacted participants' psychology of adjustment and well-being
[49]	Facer-Childs <i>et al.</i>	Quantitative	Time adjustment is an indicator of a person's mental health
[50]	Hammarlund <i>et al.</i>	Qualitative	Internal and external demands influence a person's psychological well-being
[51]	Weber <i>et al.</i>	Quantitative	Isolation does not affect mood and emotions
[52]	Martini <i>et al.</i>	Quantitative	Job demands and resources often overlook relationships with external users (students), which can play an important role in university teachers' perceptions
[53]	Brown <i>et al.</i>	Quantitative	Future work could determine whether interventions on emotion regulation strategies or heart rate variability (HRV) can change these personally over time
[54]	Demerouti	Quantitative	Maintaining high levels of well-being and performance while working from home and how to improve this using evidence-based self-coaching interventions

3.2. Discussion

External demands of learners refer to the expectations and requirements placed on learners from outside sources, such as educational policies, institutions, or collaborative partners. These external demands can influence the learning process and student outcomes. Learners may need to navigate and negotiate these external demands to align them with their goals and strategies. The interaction between external demands and the learner's goals and strategies can be seen as a process of constructing coherence, in which the learner and the educational institution work together to match external requirements and the learner's needs. Learners can benefit from the support of external representations, collaboration scripts, and content schemas to help them focus on important aspects of the task and improve collaboration outcomes [55]. However, learners may also experience difficulty in extracting and integrating information from complex displays, interacting effectively with media-rich environments, and monitoring and organizing their learning activities [56]. Today's students face various external demands that can impact their psychological well-being. First, high academic pressure is one of the main problems. Students are often faced with expectations to achieve high performance on tests and assignments, which can create excessive workloads. High achievement standards and a busy curriculum can trigger stress, anxiety, and insecurity regarding their academic performance.

In addition, expectations from the family environment can also be a significant source of external demands. Parents often have certain expectations regarding their child's academic performance or future career choices. These high expectations can pressure students, especially if they do not match their interests or abilities. A family environment that lacks emotional support can also contribute to students' psychological instability. The influence of peers and social media is another aspect that needs to be considered. Learners are exposed to certain standards of beauty, lifestyle, and achievement that are often idealized on social media. Intense social comparison among peers and exposure to perfect images on social media can create feelings of inferiority and self-doubt that negatively impact psychological well-being. The analysis results of articles that have been carried out show that comprehensive data related to demands has been obtained, showing that women, humans, and adults are the main focus of research, each covering a certain percentage. Furthermore, the factor analysis overview shows the complexity of external demands by presenting various aspects that can be used as a basis for joint research. The article's findings highlight internal and external support, job control, social media use, and individual differences in emotion regulation that influence external demands. The main findings of the analysis show that: i) internal and external support are related to job satisfaction; ii) low job control and high job demands are prognostic factors for low well-being; iii) social media use is associated with work demands; iv) external and internal conditions influence external demands; and v) individual differences in emotion regulation in response to adverse work conditions.

This analysis's results align with several previous research findings that explain that these pressures can disrupt student-centered practices, a core value of the student affairs profession [57]. Likewise, teacher educators in Swedish preschool teacher education felt a lack of support from the faculty council and their offices, which contributed to tensions and made the teacher education program fragile [58]. Other research also explains that the influence of external demands on students' well-being and academic performance is an essential aspect of the educational context. Students can experience fatigue due to high personal demands, exacerbated by the perception of study load [59]. In addition, various external stressors such as illness, loss of family members, caregiving responsibilities, and housing instability can affect students' time and energy for studying [60]. The importance of appraisal of individual demands emerges in determining the extent to which students feel stress, while social support is a key factor in reducing inhibiting appraisals and increasing well-being [61]. Further findings show that external feedback and knowledge positively influence students' motivation and learning, especially those who face difficulties [62].

Apart from the research above, other research explains that external demands from the family can significantly impact academic performance. Research has shown that parental involvement and family socioeconomic status are important factors in a child's educational journey, with a positive correlation between family background and student academic performance [63]. Academic pressure, which can stem from family expectations, has been found to have both positive and negative effects on academic achievement. Appropriate levels of academic stress can improve performance, but when stress exceeds a certain threshold, it can have negative impacts [64]. Family factors such as family structure, parental relationships, and family economic status can directly and indirectly influence academic performance. For example, family income and educational investment directly influence academic performance, while other factors, such as family structure and relationships, can influence children's physical and psychological conditions, thereby affecting their academic performance [65]. Additionally, academic and family stress has been found to cause depression among students, negatively affecting their academic performance [66]. However, one study found that family type did not significantly affect academic performance [67]. These findings provide a deeper understanding of the complexity of external demands on students, emphasizing the need to provide appropriate support to improve their well-being and academic achievement.

Various alternatives can be implemented to handle external demands that occur on students, either through individual, group, or classical services. This condition aligns with previous research findings, which explain that service interventions appropriate to external demands on students involve establishing an independent system, setting specific targets, ensuring consistency in providing support, and an effective communication system [68]. Psychological interventions with college students are beneficial in promoting mental health and preparing them for professional challenges [69]. In the context of a foreign language program, one study found that a community intervention that promoted client demand led to increased knowledge and demand for treatment practices, resulting in increased service provision [70]. Special education plays a central role in addressing the problems of students with developmental disabilities, and reforms that advance the goal of helping these students have successful school experiences are beneficial [71]. A holistic approach to education, which involves understanding students' psychological needs, is key. The need for mental health support in the school environment, guidance that recognizes the diversity of potential and interests of students, and public awareness about the impact of external demands will help create an environment that supports positive growth and psychological well-being of students.

This research provides valuable contributions in three aspects: practical, theoretical, and methodological. In practical or empirical contributions, research provides an empirical picture of how external demands influence students' psychological well-being. This contribution can be the basis for designing appropriate interventions and strategies in the field of education. The research findings also highlight the importance of collaboration between schools, families, and communities in addressing external demands, providing implications for developing holistic programs and policies. The theoretical contribution of this research enriches our understanding of the factors that influence students' psychological well-being, especially those related to external demands from the learning, family, and social environment. These findings also contribute to developing theories and models that explain the relationships between external demands, emotion regulation, social support, job control, and students' psychological well-being. In its methodological contribution, this study uses a SLR approach to synthesize various empirical studies, providing a comprehensive picture of the impact of external demands on students' psychological well-being. Using data analysis tools such as Biblioshiny and ATLAS.ti also provides a reference for similar research in the future.

In addition, this research also provides significant practical implications for educational practice and policy. Research findings emphasize the importance of creating learning environments that support student well-being by strategically managing external demands and providing appropriate support. In addition, this research encourages the development of interventions and programs involving parents, teachers, and the community to address students' external demands, such as stress management training, counseling, and emotion regulation skills. These implications can shape educational policies that pay more attention to aspects of students' psychological well-being, such as setting balanced workload standards, providing adequate counseling services, and increasing awareness about the impact of external demands on students' mental health. For educational practitioners, this research highlights the importance of creating inclusive learning environments, providing adequate support and resources, and considering individual differences in dealing with external demands. Overall, this research provides an important basis for developing educational strategies and policies that are more effective in addressing the impact of external demands on students' psychological well-being.

4. CONCLUSION

The research results show that external demands on students significantly impact their learning process and psychological well-being. These demands can come from various sources, including educational policies, institutions, and expectations from the family environment and social pressure. Learners must navigate and negotiate these demands to align with their learning goals and strategies. The complexity of interactions between external demands and learner goals illustrates a process of establishing coherence in which learners and educational institutions collaborate to find a balance between external requirements and learning needs. The main challenges students face include high academic pressure, expectations from the family environment, and the influence of peers and social media. High expectations for academic performance can create an excessive workload, causing stress, anxiety, and insecurity related to academic performance. High expectations from the family environment can also add pressure, especially if they do not match students' interests or abilities. The influence of social media and social comparison can create feelings of inferiority and self-doubt, which hurt students' psychological well-being. Mental health interventions must be implemented in the school environment to help students overcome academic pressure and other external demands. These programs may include psychological support, counseling, and a holistic approach to understanding an individual's psychological needs. In addition, improving the support system between schools, families, and communities is crucial.

Collaboration between stakeholders can create an environment that supports students' positive growth and psychological well-being. Teachers and educational staff also need to receive training to identify and overcome the external demands faced by students, with a deep understanding of individual psychological needs, to create more effective learning strategies. Increasing public awareness about the impact of external demands on students is very important so society can provide better support. Education also needs to adopt a holistic approach that focuses on the academic aspect and pays attention to students' psychological and emotional needs by recognizing the diversity of their potential and interests. These steps hope to create a more supportive educational environment, promote students' psychological well-being, and help them cope with external demands more effectively.

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